

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Insight into the Mechanism of Calcium-Induced Blockage of Gramicidin A Ion Channels

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EIS

The impedance spectra were analyzed by fitting an equivalent circuit model, shown in Figure S1, to the experimental data using the ZSimpWin software (AMETEK, USA). In this model, R_{sol} represents the resistance of the solvent, R_{mem} corresponds to the resistance of the membrane, Q_{mem} is a constant phase element (CPE) accounting for the capacitive behavior of the membrane, and Q_{sp} is a CPE representing the submembrane region between the bilayer and the Au(111) surface.

Figure S1. Equivalent circuit model used for electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data fitting. Circuit elements include resistive and constant phase components, as defined in the above text. This model is a variation of the circuit proposed by Valincius and Mickevicius[1] and is identical to the one used by the Lipkowski group for electrodes modified with lipid membranes.[2,3]

The table below presents the numerical data for each membrane system, including standard deviations. It shows the variation of the values of particular circuit components with the potential applied to the electrode. For the DOPC membrane model system, the parameter α associated with the constant phase element (CPE) of both the membrane and spacer is close to unity, indicating that these elements can be treated as capacitors. In the system incorporating gramicidin, the α parameter for the membrane remains close to one, whereas the second α parameter associated with the submembrane region is approximately 0.5, indicative of diffusive contribution. In the final case, where the ion channel is inhibited by calcium ions, the α parameter varies between 0.6 and 0.8 and, therefore, does not carry a straightforward physical interpretation.

Table 1.

DOPC					
E / mV	$Q_m / \mu\text{F} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$	α	$R_m / \text{k}\Omega \times \text{cm}^2$	$Q_{sp} / \mu\text{F} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$	α
0	$8,90 \pm 1,42$	0,98	115 ± 21	$2,25 \pm 1,5$	0,92
-100	$6,68 \pm 1,62$	0,95	141 ± 12	$1,29 \pm 1,2$	0,91
-200	$9,50 \pm 1,60$	0,95	148 ± 23	$1,04 \pm 1,2$	0,94
-300	$8,97 \pm 1,72$	0,96	172 ± 22	$1,93 \pm 0,5$	0,90
-400	$6,56 \pm 0,82$	0,98	101 ± 16	$2,50 \pm 1,5$	0,93

Table 2.

DOPC : gA 10%					
E / mV	$Q_m / \mu\text{F} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$	α	$R_m / \text{k}\Omega \times \text{cm}^2$	$Q_{sp} / \mu\text{F} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$	α
0	$9,21 \pm 3,42$	0,97	29 ± 4	$23,3 \pm 8,5$	0,54
-100	$8,65 \pm 0,71$	0,98	23 ± 3	$12,0 \pm 4,1$	0,56
-200	$9,06 \pm 1,13$	0,97	19 ± 5	$13,5 \pm 4,3$	0,49
-300	$8,07 \pm 0,74$	0,96	16 ± 6	$15,1 \pm 3,8$	0,63
-400	$11,1 \pm 4,35$	0,97	15 ± 4	$11,4 \pm 5,2$	0,56

Table 3.

DOPC : gA 10% + 1mM Ca^{2+}					
E / mV	$Q_m / \mu\text{F} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$	α	$R_m / \text{k}\Omega \times \text{cm}^2$	$Q_{sp} / \mu\text{F} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$	α

0	$8,90 \pm 0,72$	0,97	99 ± 14	$6,76 \pm 2,6$	0,78
-100	$6,68 \pm 1,58$	0,98	102 ± 10	$5,92 \pm 3,1$	0,68
-200	$9,50 \pm 2,60$	0,97	95 ± 5	$7,07 \pm 4,5$	0,66
-300	$8,97 \pm 1,72$	0,96	96 ± 5	$4,86 \pm 4,2$	0,74
-400	$6,56 \pm 0,82$	0,97	69 ± 4	$7,14 \pm 3,1$	0,75

Surface Pressure Measurements

Additional information on the elastic properties of the monolayer at the air-water interface may be obtained based on compression modulus (C_s^{-1}). It may be calculated as the reciprocal of compressibility [4,5]:

$$C_s^{-1} = -A \left(\frac{d\pi}{dA} \right)_T$$

where C_s^{-1} is compression modulus, A is area per molecule and π is surface pressure. The values of C_s^{-1} provide information on the possible phases of a monolayer, which include the gas phase (G) with the values between 0 - 12.5 mN/m, liquid-expanded phase (LE) from 12.5 to 50 mN/m, liquid-condensed phase (LC) between 100 and 250 mN/m and solid phase (S) above 250 mN/m [6]. Additionally, the minima on the compression modulus vs. surface pressure (C_s^{-1} vs. π) plots prove the existence of phase transitions.

Figure S2. A) Compression modulus versus surface pressure plot, B) multiple compression-expansion cycles of DOPC-gA monolayer formed on PBS buffer subphase with and without calcium ions.

Potential-dependent SEIRA spectra

The potential-dependent SEIRA spectra showed that, within the membrane stability region, no significant changes were observed in the orientation of either lipid or peptide molecules. The spectra recorded at different potentials are presented below. The only noticeable variations appear in the O–D stretching vibration region, reflecting changes in the water content and organization at the interface.

Figure S3. Potential-dependent SEIRA spectra of the DOPC/gA bilayer recorded in 0.01 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared in D₂O. Spectrum collected at the potential of -0.1 V was used as reference.

In the case of the DOPC/gA membrane, variations in the electrode potential do not induce significant changes within the C–H stretching or amide I/II bands. This observation is consistent with the findings reported by Su et al.,[2] who demonstrated that a PC lipid membrane

containing gramicidin, deposited on a thioglucose-modified gold electrode, does not undergo notable structural rearrangements within a similar potential range — the tilt angle of both the acyl chains and the peptide remains virtually unchanged or negligible. The appearance of a positive band in the O-D stretching region may indicate a reorientation and/or a slight increase in the amount of water within the interfacial region, which aligns well with the observed decrease in membrane resistance (increased permeability for water and ion flow).

Figure S4. Potential-dependent SEIRA spectra of the DOPC/gA bilayer recorded in 0.01 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared in D₂O, in the presence of Ca²⁺ cations. Spectrum collected at the potential of -0.1 V was used as reference.

In the case of the DOPC/gA membrane in the presence of calcium ions, no potential-dependent changes are observed in the C-H stretching and amide I/II spectral regions as well. Similar to the system without calcium ions, minor variations are detected in the O-D stretching region; however, in this case, they exhibit an opposite trend, with the appearance of a negative band,

which may also reflect the reorientation and/or depletion of water from the interfacial region. This observation appears consistent with the membrane dehydration induced by calcium ions. Moreover, the lowering of the electrode potential may facilitate the attraction of positively charged calcium ions towards the membrane.

Figure S5. (A) Time-dependent SEIRA spectra of the DOPC/gA bilayer recorded in 0.01 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared in D₂O, before and after exposure to Ca²⁺ cations (exposure time is given at each spectrum). (B) integrated intensity of the bands appearing at C-H stretching region shown in panel (A) as a function of exposure time. The spectra were recorded under electrochemical control at the potential of -100 mV vs. Ag|AgCl.

Exposure of the DOPC/gA membrane to calcium cations induces only minor changes in the spectral region corresponding to C–H stretching vibrations (Figure S5A). Specifically, there is no shift in the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{CH}_2)$ bands; however, a slight decrease in their integrated intensity can be observed (Figure S5B), which may indicate a small reduction in the tilt angle of a certain population of acyl chains relative to the surface normal. Although SEIRAS is not suitable for providing quantitative information on the order parameter, we can nevertheless infer that the observed changes qualitatively correspond to a slight increase in membrane ordering within the hydrocarbon chains. This effect is very subtle, however, it is reproducible and consistent with the observed decrease in the molecular area of the membrane-forming molecules in the presence of calcium ions (see Figure 6 in the main text).

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